

EOSC SOA Project Report #4: EOSC Gravity

Supporting the EOSC Partnership in further consolidating the coordination and sustainability of the EOSC ecosystem

About

- ❖ EOSC Gravity is a Coordination and Support Action (CSA) awarded through the Horizon Europe call HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-02, [Supporting the EOSC Partnership in further consolidating the coordination and sustainability of the EOSC ecosystem](#).
- ❖ The project supports the transition of the European co-programmed Partnership for EOSC into its new governance and funding framework for EOSC post-2027 by pulling the communities of EOSC stakeholders together.
- ❖ Building on the frameworks established by [EOSC Focus](#), EOSC Gravity will establish new stakeholder engagement channels and, via open calls, provide funding to support the EOSC Federation Build-up Phase by supporting the enrolment of future EOSC Nodes and fostering inter-project collaboration. Further, EOSC Gravity will support the revision of SRIA 2.0.
- ❖ The further evolution of the EOSC Federation will be charted through measures to monitor and report on EOSC Partnership KPIs and to establish a methodology for assessing the impact of EOSC.

Project Activities

EOSC Gravity supports the [European co-programmed Partnership for EOSC](#) in maintaining a consistent flow of information on the status of EOSC, and helps to generate strategic recommendations through the SRIA to ensure a smooth transition to a new governance and funding model beyond 2027.

EOSC Gravity leverages and expands upon engagement mechanisms established by [EOSC Focus](#) to extend its impact.

EOSC Gravity supports the EOSC Federation through open calls, encouraging the development of EOSC Nodes.

EOSC Gravity promotes collaboration of INFRAEOSC projects, and contributes to the revision of the [EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#) (SRIA 2.0) and the corresponding update to the Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR). It will drive the evolution of the [EOSC Federation](#) by monitoring [EOSC Partnership Key Performance Indicators](#) (KPIs) and by developing a robust methodology for assessing EOSC's broader impact.

Project Factsheet

- ❖ **Duration:** 31 months, 1 June 2025 to 31 December 2027
- ❖ **Budget:** €4.66 million
- ❖ **Funding source:** Horizon Europe
- ❖ **Call identifier:** HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-02
- ❖ **Grant agreement ID:** 101188045
- ❖ **Project title:** Supporting the EOSC Partnership in further consolidating the coordination and sustainability of the EOSC ecosystem

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Consortium

[EOSC Association](#) (EOSC-A), Coordinator | Belgium
[Graz University of Technology](#) (TU Graz) | Austria
[European Science Foundation](#) (ESF) | France
[Athena Research Centre](#) | Greece
[Professional Mobile and Network Service Provider](#) (Pro-M) | Hungary
[Trust-IT Services](#) | Italy
[COMMPLA](#) | Italy
[EGI Foundation](#) (EGI) | Netherlands
[National Science Centre](#) (NCN) | Poland
[Switch](#) | Switzerland

Spotlight: The EOSC Winter School

The EOSC Winter School, now moving towards its third edition, in January 2026, is an in-person format created by the EOSC Focus project in response to collaboration needs among Horizon Europe EOSC-related projects. Participants include representatives from the EOSC-A Board and Secretariat, the European Commission, the HE EOSC-related projects, the OAEs, and the EOSC-A Task Forces, who engage in hands-on work to identify common challenges and collaboration opportunities, and address the sustainability of project outputs, to achieve convergence and support the build-up phase of the EOSC Federation.

Spotlight: TU Graz in EOSC Gravity

TU Graz, represented by the [RDM Team](#), is the only Austrian project partner involved in EOSC Gravity. As Pillar 3 lead and T4.2 and T5.2 task lead, TU Graz is responsible for sustaining inter-project collaboration across the channels established by the EOSC Focus project (Opportunity Area Expert Groups, HE Technology Group, HE Impact Group, and Technical Coordinators Group). Further, TU Graz is involved in the creation and updating the EOSC Federation Handbook, as well as in T1.2 of Gravity (updating the Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) 2.0).

Impact on EOSC

EOSC Gravity supports the EOSC governance framework by developing policies and procedures, growing the number of Nodes in the [EOSC Federation](#), and supporting the implementation of coherent funding models to enable smooth access to data and services.

EOSC Gravity supports the implementation of new EOSC coordination mechanisms, promotes knowledge sharing and mutual learning through the EOSC Academy, monitors the evolution of EOSC, and facilitates impact assessment of the initiatives developed under geo-engagement activities.

EOSC Gravity strengthens collaboration across existing [INFRAEOSC projects](#), ensuring better alignment, shared goals, and efficient resource use. This objective underpins the creation of a more unified and coherent EOSC ecosystem, ensuring collaboration with the [EOSC-A Task Forces](#).

A central focus of EOSC Gravity is to support and engage the diverse community of stakeholders who make up the EOSC ecosystem, ensuring they are informed, equipped, and actively involved in shaping its future.

Additional Information

Additional information on the project, its objectives, project structure, and consortium, can be found on the [EOSC Association project website](#).